

Going beyond statistical rituals: Improving the understanding of statistics using blog posts and workshops

Xenia Schmalz

Department of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry, Psychosomatics and Psychotherapy, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Germany, xenia.schmalz@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Keywords

Replication crisis, statistical literacy, p-value,

Purpose of this paper

In recent years, it has become increasingly clear that many empirical findings in psychological science are not replicable (Open Science Collaboration, 2015). This is problematic, because this suggest that psychological theories, which are often used for high-stake decision making, may be based on effects that, in reality, do not exist. The proximal causes of the replication crisis have been identified as publication bias (selective publication of significant results), questionable research practices (tweaking the data and analyses until one obtains a significant result), low power (too few participants to yield a high probability of obtaining an effect of interest) and hypothesising after results are known (HARKing; writing a rationale for a study after the data has already been analysed) (Bishop, 2019). To a large extent, these issues can be traced back to a poor understanding of statistics.

Design/methodology/approach

Improving statistical training in higher education provides a potentially powerful cure to the replication crisis: specifically, researchers need to develop a deep understanding which goes beyond the calculation of a single summary statistic such as a p -value (Gigerenzer, 2018). In a series of workshops and blog post, I aim to provide mathematically correct but intuitive explanations of basic statistical concepts which are often used for inference. For example,

questionable research practices are often a result of a lack of understanding of how the p -value works (Simmons, Nelson, & Simonsohn, 2011): It is unintuitive why it is incorrect to calculate a p -value and determine whether to continue testing depending on whether the result is approaching significance or whether it is already significant. It is more intuitive, however, to think of an example of tossing a coin: if I promise to correctly guess five outcomes in a row, I will achieve this if I continue tossing the coin *until* I obtain five correct guesses in a row, even though I lack any clairvoyant powers. The coin analogy can therefore provide an intuitive explanation about why optional stopping is inappropriate when relying on a p -value for inference.

Implications

The development of such materials is the first step to improving statistical literacy. Here, the challenge is to find a level of depth that does not oversimplify complex concepts which could, in turn, lead to an increase in the inappropriate use of statistical methods, while at the same time avoiding technicalities that are irrelevant to researchers. The next step is open dissemination. Here, there are several options, each with benefits and drawbacks. For example, workshops and seminars allow the attendees to ask for clarifications, but have strong limitations in terms of accessibility. These are issues that warrant further discussion.

References

- Bishop, D. (2019). Rein in the four horsemen of irreproducibility. *Nature*, 568, 435.
- Gigerenzer, G. (2018). Statistical rituals: The replication delusion and how we got there. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 1(2), 198-218.
- Open Science Collaboration. (2015). Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science. *Science*, 349(6251), aac4716.
- Simmons, J. P., Nelson, L. D., & Simonsohn, U. (2011). False-positive psychology: Undisclosed flexibility in data collection and analysis allows presenting anything as significant. *Psychological Science*, 22(11), 1359-1366.

Suggested Citation

Schmalz, Z.. (2019). Going beyond statistical rituals: Improving the understanding of statistics using blog posts and workshops. *Research Symposium – Open Practices in Education (OPINE)*. 14-15 Nov 2019, Frankfurt a. M., Germany. [doi see Zenodo]